

The Effect of the Company's Cultural Diversity on Restaurant Employees Performance

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ABSTRACT: This study looked at how managing organizational cultural diversity affects restaurant employees' performance. The study's main objective is to provide in-depth information about workplace cultural diversity. It seeks to create a precise set of rules to help organizations all over the world embrace cultural diversity. The respondents' demographic profile, including their gender, age, religion, ethnicity, race, and civil status, was successfully evaluated by the researchers using a questionnaire. This information is crucial for assessing the respondents' differences and how those differences affect their performance at work. The Likert Scale Method is used by the researchers to gauge the respondents' level of agreement with each statement provided in order to determine how cultural diversity affects productivity at work. The study explores how cultural diversity affects employees' performance and productivity, how employees view their organization's management strategy for managing cultural diversity, and how employees' experiences with cultural diversity in the workplace. According to the study, women make up the majority of respondents, who are between the ages of 20 and 30, among those who work in restaurants. The majority of respondents, according to the study, are Roman Catholic, Tagalog, and Asian. Regarding their civil status, all of the respondents are single. On the other hand, the majority of respondents considered their restaurant fosters teamwork by allowing diverse employees to share ideas and knowledge in order to find the best way to solve a problem, resulting in a better outcome on tasks. When it comes to respondents' level of agreement, the majority of respondents believe that organizational cultural diversity benefits restaurant employees' productivity. According to the study's findings, cultural diversity management training or education may enhance workers' performance at work. They will be better able to identify their own strengths and weaknesses if they have an understanding of cultural diversity. When a workplace is managed effectively, it promotes the growth of new ideas, knowledge, abilities, and working methods. The success and profitability of an organization are also influenced by cultural diversity, and productivity is increased in an environment free from cultural prejudice.

KEYWORDS: Employee engagement, employee performance, cultural diversity, organizational culture, restaurant employees

INTRODUCTION

Workplace diversity describes the similarities and differences between employees that are based on factors such as age, culture, physical traits and limitations, race, religion, gender, and sexual orientation. Every person is unique. People vary not only in terms of their gender, ethnicity, language, psychological, and emotional traits, but also in terms of their perspectives and biases. As a result of a multicultural workplace, employees deal with a variety of issues at work. Each employee must be effective in their performance in the sector in order to meet organizational goals, even though some members of the diverse workforce may experience less cooperation from their coworkers. Employee termination is not a choice, though.

The study's overarching goal is to investigate the impact of organizational cultural diversity on restaurant workforce productivity. This study addressed the following questions: Are there organizational cultural differences among restaurant workers? Does organizational culture diversity affect restaurant teamwork? Does organizational cultural diversity have a significant impact on the productivity of the restaurant workforce?

The study sought to investigate the impact of managing organizational cultural diversity on restaurant workers' productivity. The primary goal of the study was to provide comprehensive information about cultural diversity in the workplace. It also established a clear guideline to assist various organizations around the world in embracing cultural diversity.

According to Patrick, H.A., et al. (2012), while most employees (diversity optimists) are confident in their ability to deal with diversity, only a small percentage of employees have grasped it, adjusted, and are enthusiastic about working and utilizing positive workplace diversity (diversity optimists). Despite the challenges of diversity, having a diverse workforce may result in

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good trade-offs due to obvious benefits. In today's global environment, a diverse workforce is appealing. Diversity in the workplace provides benefits such as the ability to adapt quickly, the availability of a broader range of alternative problem-solving strategies, in-service sourcing, and resource allocation.

Additional benefits include a broader range of services, a diverse set of skills and experiences, as well as different languages, cultures, and viewpoints. Because of the diverse range of knowledge and expertise, as well as different problem-solving methods, tasks are carried out more efficiently and effectively (Greenberg, 2015). Organizations with a diverse workforce can bring a broader range of perspectives to the problem-solving of human resource hiring, retention, and allocation. It is also claimed by McKinsey & Company (2018) that businesses with a diverse workforce outperform their peers financially by 35%. Another potential financial benefit of wide diversity is cost savings. (O'Donovan, 2017).

METHODS

A quantitative approach was used in this study. According to Apuke (2017) study, quantitative research is the process of quantifying and evaluating variables in order to obtain results. It entails examining numerical data with statistical tools to answer questions such as who, how much, what, when, how many, and how. It also describes the procedures for gathering numerical data in order to fully comprehend a problem or event.

The researchers used the Descriptive Research Method, with the goal of providing comprehensive information about cultural diversity in workplaces to employees. Additionally, assisting businesses and organizations in developing cultural diversity plans that will allow them to evolve, innovate, solve problems, and become more efficient in the workplace. It entailed recording, data collection, data analysis, and data presentation. The survey method, also known as the Normative Survey, was used in descriptive research. As the primary data collection tool for this study, the researchers conducted and collected a survey. They distributed close-ended questionnaires to fifty (50) respondents via Google Forms via the Messenger application to make them more accessible. Before taking the survey, researchers explained the questionnaire to each respondent individually and clarified the contents. The researchers also discussed the ethical considerations such as anonymity and confidentiality. Random sampling was used to select respondents. The survey questionnaire is divided into two sections. The first section contains the data of the respondents. The second part is set of questions; the researchers used the Likert scale, a five or seven-item agreement scale commonly used to assess respondents' approval of various statements. The Likert scale assumes that an attitude's strength or intensity is linear. It ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree, and it requires that the point of view be quantified.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interestingly, the findings revealed that 55% of the respondents are Agree, 15% are Strongly Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree, respectively, that their employer has put in place a policy/measures to manage cultural diversity. Thirty-five (35) percent of the respondents are both Strongly Agree and Agree that the restaurant they are currently working at promotes a management style that accepts and appreciates the unique differences in individuals, and twenty (20) percent are Disagree, and ten (10) percent are Strongly Disagree. The findings also revealed that only forty-five (45) percent of the respondents are Strongly Agree, twenty-five (25) percent are Agree that the restaurant they are currently working at has a work environment with no barriers such as communication, promotional opportunities, working relationships, etc. created by cultural differences among individuals and twenty (20) percent are Disagree, and ten (10) percent of the respondents are Disagree. On the other hand, both forty (40) percent of the respondents are Strongly agreed and agree that the restaurant they are currently working at provides opportunities to develop and grow at all levels without cultural barriers or discrimination, and ten (10) percent of the respondents are both Disagree and Strongly Disagree. It was revealed that forty (40) percent of the respondents are both Strongly Agree and Agree that their employer recognizes their culture. As a result, they currently have a sense of belonging to the restaurant they are working in, and ten (10) percent are both Disagree and Strongly Disagree. Also, it was found that fifty-five (55) percent of the respondents are Strongly Agree, thirty (30) percent are Agree that the restaurant they are working at has a work environment that is free from cultural discrimination and ten (10) percent of the respondents are Strongly Disagree. Forty-five (45) percent of the respondents are Strongly Agree, forty (40) percent are Agree that the restaurant values (as employees to improved performance) consider their cultural values, and 10% are Disagree, and 5% are Strongly Disagree. These findings showed that only almost 50% of the respondents are Strongly Agree, 30% are Agree that cultural diversity in the restaurant they are working at increases the productivity of the organization, and 10% are both Disagree and Strongly Disagree. Only 45% are Strongly Agree, 40% are Agree that having a different cultural understanding and language allow their work to provide customer service if there's a foreign customer while another 5% are Disagree, and 10% of the respondents are Strongly Disagree. When it comes to their strengths and weaknesses are well complimented by other cultures; 55% of the respondents are Agree, 30% are Strongly Agree, 10% are Disagree, and 5% are Strongly Disagree. For the effective

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and productive when they work in a group of mixed cultures, 45% of the respondents are Agree, 25% are Strongly Agree, 20% are Disagree, and 10% are Strongly Disagree. There were 60% of the respondents are Agree, 15% are Strongly Agree, that they can better communicate the information about their job to other cultures as much as they do to employees of their culture, while 25% of the respondents are Disagree. These findings show that 50% of the respondents are Agree, 15% are Strongly Agree that cultural stereotypes still exist and affect the functionality and relationship within employees and 25% percent are Disagree, 10% of the respondents are Strongly Disagree. However, only 40% of the respondents are both Strongly Agree and Agree that cultural diversity helps them develop new skills and ways to work and 10% are Disagree and Strongly Disagree. Therefore, a total of 50% of the respondents are Strongly Agree, 35% are Agree that a culturally diverse workforce brings new ideas and different knowledge to the employees, and ten 10% of the respondents are Disagree, and 5% are Strongly Disagree. Fifty (50) percent of the respondents are Agree that cultural diversity management program/education would enhance their performance in doing their job, and another 35% are Strongly Agree, 10% are Disagree, and 5% of the respondents are Strongly Disagree. These findings showed that more than half or 65% of the respondents are Agree, 25% are Strongly Agree that being in a culturally diverse environment triggers their innovative and creative thinking when doing their job and 10% are Disagree.

It was also found out that only 55% of the respondents are Agree and another 25% are Strongly Agree that cultural diversity management has a direct influence on employee and skills retention and 15% are Disagree, 5% of the respondents are Strongly Disagree. These findings showed that only almost 45% of the respondents are Strongly Agree, 40% are Agree that a well-managed culturally diverse workforce contributes to the success and profitability of this business, and 15% of the respondents are Disagree. But there were 50% of the respondents are Strongly Agree, 30% agree that understanding cultural diversity will help them realize their strengths and weaknesses when doing their job. The remaining 15% are Disagree, and 5% are Strongly Disagree.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Around the world, finding a job is far more difficult for women than for men. Many women face job discrimination because others assume that they are incapable of doing what men can do. They often feel that women are weak and that certain professions are unsuitable for women. Despite that, according to the researchers' data, female was the most dominant gender, with 26 or 55% of the respondents currently working in a restaurant. It indicates that the gap and gender discrimination in the workplace is now reducing, and women have more opportunities to enjoy equal rights in terms of compensation and benefits, training, development, better promotion, and appraisals.

The age of the respondents ranges from 20-30 or 95%, the period when most of the people need to work to meet their financial obligations and provide financially for their family. This result also indicates that due to differences in the respondents' age, some workplace issues might happen, such as older employees may require more time to adjust to recent technological advancements than younger employees. In addition to this, more youthful employees do not feel valued or respected when collaborating with older employees because of their age. They may be resentful of the more senior employees' greater authority. Employees may have a conflict with their ideas. Still, on the other hand, different experiences, expectations, styles, and perspectives provided by age diversity in the workplace may become a source of strength and innovation for the organization when all these differences are addressed and appropriately managed.

Based on the data, 38 or 75% of the respondents are Roman Catholic. While on the other hand, there are only 12 or 25% Christian. It shows that Roman Catholicism is the most common religion in the workplace. As a result, they are the least likely to experience religious discrimination because they share the same religious beliefs. Besides, 100% of the respondents' ethnicity is Tagalog, which illustrates that the most common ethnicity here in the Philippines is Tagalog. Workers frequently share the same language, allowing for accessible communication and avoiding misunderstandings in the workplace. In terms of race, all the respondents are Asian, indicating that most workers in the Philippines are Asian and share the same physical characteristics that preclude racial discrimination.

The respondents' civil status indicates that 100% of them are single, allowing them to spend as much time pursuing their careers. It makes the single workers focus more on their job than those married and have children to take care of. As a result, the researchers conclude that most single employees are more likely to be promoted than married employees. But on the other hand, married employees receive more paid time off than single employees and more significant employer contributions to their healthcare and pension programs. Most employers provide higher benefits to married employees than to single ones.

Based on the responses of the respondents, the researchers concluded that the respondents agreed that their restaurant promotes a management style that accepts and appreciates the unique differences in individuals. It also shows that their organization provides opportunities to develop and grow at all levels without cultural barriers or discrimination. Also, most

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restaurants where the respondents work have a working environment free from cultural discrimination. They agreed that cultural diversity increases the organization's productivity.

Moreover, the respondents also agreed that they are more productive when collaborating with their co-workers who share their cultural beliefs because they can easily communicate with other employees. Despite that, they also believe that when a culturally diverse workplace is properly managed, it will help them develop new ideas, knowledge, skills, and new ways to work.

In addition to this, the respondents agreed that cultural diversity management program/education would enhance their performance in doing their job. Aside from that, cultural diversity helps them be innovative and increase their creativity. Also, cultural diversity management directly influences employee and skills retention. It also contributes to the success and profitability of the organization as well. The respondents also agreed that understanding cultural diversity would help them realize their strengths and weaknesses when doing their job.

Based on the results, the researchers recommend that entrepreneurs choose employees based on their skills and capabilities rather than their gender when it comes to job opportunities. It will help to reduce and lessen discrimination towards women and men. There must also be an activity for the employees (e.g., team training activities) grouped by different ages to help them improve their relationships as coworkers. It will make them comfortable with each other and lessen their conflicts without thinking about their age gap. As the researchers observe in the results, Roman Catholicism got the least likely to experience religious discrimination because most of them share the same religious beliefs. Researchers suggest that everyone should respect each other's religion, preferences, and beliefs to have unity and understanding of the differences. The researchers also recommend that every restaurant, not just in the locality of the study, should promote a discrimination-free environment so that workers can excel and work efficiently. On top of that, workers should also feel comfortable and confident with their unique differences as it can help to normalize appreciating the notable differences in individuals.

Moreover, the researchers would like to suggest to the restaurant to have a seminar for their employees on how they will deal with everyone's differences and have a team-building or sports activities, so the workers will have bonding with each other and motivated to their work so that their employees can bond and figure out how to build relationships as co-workers despite their differences and to create teamwork for the success of their organization. The researchers recommend that the restaurant have a training program for their staff and employees. To improve their skills and gain access to decision-making to develop innovations. This training program will contribute to the organization's success and allow them to categorize the strengths and weaknesses of each other within their industry.

LIMITATIONS

Overall, this paper contribute to the understanding about cultural diversity in the workplace particularly in the restaurant sector. However, the study considers only 50 workers which is quite small for a quantitative study. Also, the findings from this study might not be applicable across other sectors.

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